

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.362 Max: 62.389	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1466 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		
				In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 0060-62
DEFINITION tiles within cut in sewer infant burial				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1408	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1483	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
						Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)							
Northern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Western Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		grave 45		
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):				
Is abutted by:			Abuts:				
Is covered by: 1408			Covers: 1478				
Is cut by:			Cuts:				
Is filled by:			Fills: 1483				
OBSERVATIONS uncovered in wet conditions after rain storm							
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: located centrally within Area B, a bit north of center, within sewer channel SU ___ within cut SU ___ under fill SU 1408 Shape: irregular (tiles have broken edges)							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):							
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight							
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping							
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular							
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
Observations:							

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: *tile placed North-South*

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify) *tile*

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions: *none*

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing: _____

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type _____

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

length 54cm width 28.5cm

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

see reverse.

INTERPRETATION

Two large tile fragments used as covers above an infant burial in an imbrex

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *S. Jon*

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Entered by

on